

Fingertip Injuries: From Current Epidemiology in Mexico to Reconstructive Options. A Literature Review

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ABSTRACT

Each year, fingertip injuries are a frequent cause of amputation in thousands of individuals, with significant repercussions on occupational and daily life. These injuries present in a wide spectrum, ranging from simple lacerations to major tissue avulsions and crush injuries.

The fingertip contains a high density of sensory nerve endings; therefore, restoration of sensation is a primary goal of treatment. However, other reconstructive objectives include ensuring proper nail growth with adequate bony support and preserving the anatomical contour of the fingertip.

Post-reconstructive complications may include delayed wound healing, nail deformities, hypersensitivity, residual pain, cold intolerance, wound infection, and partial or total necrosis with flap loss.

The aim of this article is to update the epidemiological data related to fingertip injuries in Mexico, as well as to describe digital anatomy, the different types of fingertip injuries, and the complications that may arise during the clinical course of these conditions.

Category: Plastic and Reconstructive Surgery

KEYWORDS: Fingertip injury, fingertip, digital amputation, hand injury, fingertip injuries, upper extremity injuries

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INTRODUCTION

The hand is the most important working tool for human beings and is frequently exposed to daily stress and a high risk of injury.

Fingertip injuries are the most common hand injuries and are defined as those affecting the distal phalanx, involving the skin, subcutaneous tissue, and/or the nail bed, with or without associated bone fracture. (1,2) These injuries most commonly result from sharp lacerations, followed by blunt trauma. Other important causes include burns, crush injuries, bites, and, less frequently, gunshot wounds. (3)

Numerous reconstructive techniques are available for fingertip injuries; however, their application must be specific and individualized for each patient. Detailed knowledge of anatomy allows the surgeon to select the most appropriate reconstructive option in order to restore both function and structural integrity of the digit. Likewise, careful evaluation

of defect characteristics—including shape, size, and the presence of bone exposure—plays a critical role in guiding reconstructive strategy, allowing tailored treatment and reducing the rate of functional and aesthetic complications. (4,5)

Epidemiology in Mexico

Hand injuries are a frequent cause of emergency department visits. In the United States, the National Electronic Injury Surveillance System (NEISS) estimates approximately 102,350 hand injury consultations per year, with a finger injury rate of nearly 200 cases per 100,000 inhabitants. Within these figures, fingertip injuries are included, as risk is significantly increased due to exposure during occupational and domestic activities in daily life. (6)

In Mexico, the figures are similarly alarming. According to data reported by the General Directorate of Health Information (Dirección General de Información en Salud,

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DGIS), during 2025 a total of 162,214 hand injuries were reported, representing approximately 14% of all injuries nationwide. Likewise, the Mexican Social Security Institute (Instituto Mexicano del Seguro Social, IMSS) reports 113,511 cases of hand injuries per year, accounting for 26.9% of all occupational accidents, confirming the close relationship between fingertip injuries and occupational activities. (7)

According to data from the reference center for plastic and reconstructive surgery in Mexico City, Hospital "Dr. Manuel Gea González," the most frequent cause of fingertip injuries is sharp lacerations (60%), followed by blunt trauma. Male patients are affected more frequently. (8,9)

In a Mexican series, Borunda Herrera (2014) identified that the third digit is the most commonly affected (15.2%); its greater length predisposes it to injury.

In the pediatric population, the predominant mechanisms of injury are crush injuries and contact with sharp objects. According to Santos-Gallegos et al., patients younger than 15 years have a significantly higher probability of sustaining fingertip injuries compared with older patients. (9)

In the economically active population, hand and fingertip injuries are primarily associated with operative occupations. The most frequent mechanism of injury is contact with machinery, particularly industrial machines (50%), saws (6.7%), and stamping machines (5.6%), underscoring the importance of industrial safety and prevention measures in reducing this type of trauma. (10)

Review

Methods

Searches were conducted in the PubMed, MEDLINE, and Cochrane databases to identify studies that met our eligibility criteria. The most recent search was performed in February 2020 using the following terms in various combinations: "fingertip," "injury," "hand," "laceration," "management," and "complications." The selection and review process was performed manually, randomly, and in a blinded fashion by four independent reviewers. Eligibility criteria included peer-reviewed studies in English addressing the anatomy, management, or complications of fingertip injuries.

Anatomy

The fingertip is a highly specialized anatomical and functional unit whose integrity is essential for fine pinch, discriminative sensation, and tactile interaction. (11)

The distal phalanx constitutes the structural bony component of the fingertip. It is dorsopalmarly flattened and distally expanded, providing support for the pulp and nail apparatus. The distal periosteum plays a key role in pulp pad stability and bone healing following trauma or resection. The intimate relationship between bone and soft tissues determines the indication for flap coverage when bone exposure is present. (12)

The pulp is composed of specialized adipose tissue organized into lobules separated by vertical fibrous septa that extend from the dermis to the periosteum of the distal phalanx. This

architecture provides resistance to skin displacement, facilitates shock absorption, and allows high tactile sensitivity. Surgically, these septa explain the limited mobility of pulp skin and the tendency toward pain in inflammatory or cicatricial processes. (11,12)

The volar skin of the fingertip is thick, glabrous, and highly specialized. It contains a high density of sweat glands and well-defined papillary ridges responsible for fingerprints. The epidermis is firmly anchored to deeper planes, influencing the choice of local advancement techniques in reconstructive management. In contrast, the distal dorsal skin is thinner, more mobile, and less resistant to load, but is essential for coverage of the nail apparatus. (12)

The nail apparatus consists of the nail matrix (germinal and sterile), nail plate, nail bed, proximal and lateral nail folds, and hyponychium. The germinal matrix, located beneath the proximal nail fold, is responsible for nail growth; injury is associated with permanent nail deformities. The nail bed contributes to adherence and sliding of the nail plate and participates in distal dorsal sensation. The hyponychium acts as a protective barrier against external agents. (12)

The blood supply of the fingertip depends on the proper digital arteries, branches of the common palmar digital arteries, which form terminal arches at the level of the distal phalanx. (12)

Venous drainage occurs through dorsal and palmar subcutaneous plexuses, whose preservation is essential to avoid venous congestion in local reconstructions. (12)

Sensory innervation is provided by the palmar digital nerves, which supply protective sensation, two-point discrimination, and fine tactile feedback. Distally, the nerves branch extensively, forming a dense sensory plexus. Preservation or reconstruction of these nerves is essential for optimal functional outcomes. (12)

Lymphatic drainage of the fingertip is superficial and accompanies the venous structures. Its compromise may promote persistent edema and delayed wound healing, particularly in complex trauma. (12)

Diagnosis

Evaluation should begin with a complete directed history: occupation, dominant hand, smoking status, comorbidities, vaccination status, and prior surgical procedures.

Fingertip injuries may present with a constellation of findings, ranging from nail matrix injury to fractures of the distal phalanx involving the tuft, shaft, base, or a combination of these.

Non-Surgical Treatment

This may be reserved for subungual hematomas involving less than 50% of the nail plate without fracture, or those greater than 50% that are asymptomatic and without fracture. Adequate analgesia should be provided with nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs or short courses of opioids. (13) Prophylactic antibiotics should be considered in contaminated wounds, bites, and avulsion injuries. Tetanus immunization is imperative.

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Surgical Treatment

Trephination of the nail plate for subungual hematoma should be performed when involvement exceeds 50%. The nail plate may be preserved if viable (i.e., without laceration and/or avulsion); otherwise, it should be removed, followed by exploration and repair of the nail bed using absorbable suture material and, when possible, splinting with the removed nail plate after proper antiseptics.

Tuft fractures of the distal phalanx are usually comminuted and may be treated with reapproximation of the nail bed and replacement of the nail plate; however, Stack splints may provide adequate immobilization.

Shaft fractures of the distal phalanx are most commonly transverse and may be treated non-surgically with immobilization for 4 weeks, provided there is no displacement and/or rotation. Alternatively, the use of two or more Kirschner wires has shown faster consolidation compared with a single wire; similar results have been reported with 23-gauge needles.

Base fractures of the distal phalanx (intra-articular) require Kirschner wire fixation and may be associated with flexor digitorum profundus (FDP) tendon insertion injuries, where tendon insertion causes avulsion of a bony fragment. This injury may be classified according to the Leddy-Packer classification, based on tendon retraction and involvement of the vincular system. (14)

Type	Description	Vincular System Involved
I	FDP tendon retracts to the palm	Long vincula / Short vincula
II	FDP tendon retracts to the A3 pulley	Short vincula
III	FDP tendon retracts to A4	None
IV	FDP tendon retracts to the palm	Variable
V	Avulsion of bony fragment with concomitant distal fracture	Variable

FDP: Flexor digitorum profundus

Type I injuries require intervention within one week using a pull-out technique with a dorsal button. Extensor mechanism injuries may or may not involve a bony avulsion fragment. Closed injuries may be managed with immobilization for up to 8 weeks; however, surgical intervention with Kirschner wires or open reduction and internal fixation with screws should be considered when more than 30% of the articular surface is involved. (15)

Tissue defects of the finger may be managed depending on defect size. Wounds without bone or tendon exposure and measuring less than 1 cm may be treated by secondary intention. Otherwise, a flap should be considered, preferably harvested from the same digit, followed by adjacent-digit flaps or flaps from the ipsilateral hand.

Among surgical options, the Atasoy flap is used for oblique volar defects, and the Kutler flap for transverse volar defects; both are indicated for limited wounds <1 cm involving exposed bone. Advantages include low-to-moderate technical demand, minimal donor-site morbidity, and reduced hook or parrot-beak deformity.

The palmar advancement neurocutaneous pedicled flap, also known as the Moberg flap, is a workhorse for reconstruction of thumb fingertip defects, particularly in proximal volar-angled defects smaller than 1.5 cm.

Other reconstructive options include the homodigital reverse-flow dorsoulnar artery flap (Brunelli) and dorsoradial artery flap (Moschella). Indications include fingertip defects up to 1.5 × 3 cm, with careful planning of pedicle rotation based on the arcade proximal to the nail fold, or defects of 1.5 × 1.5 cm based on the dorsopalmar anastomosis at the neck of the proximal phalanx. Advantages include confinement of the donor area to the same digit, a single-stage procedure, and the possibility of obtaining a sensate flap. (16)

The heterodigital proximally based island flap (Littler flap) is used for small-to-moderate defects requiring sensate reconstruction. If dissection is extended to the superficial palmar arch, a flap harvested from the middle phalanx of the third or fourth digit can reach the thumb pulp without difficulty. It depends on one of the digital neurovascular bundles of a healthy digit, traditionally the radial bundle of the fourth digit or the ulnar bundle of the third digit, as these are located on the non-dominant side of less dominant fingers. Additionally, sensitivity in these regions, like that of the thumb, depends on branches of the median nerve, theoretically facilitating cortical adaptation. Longer digits also provide a better arc of rotation; however, if required, the flap may be harvested from any digital bundle of any finger. (17)

Complications

After fingertip amputation, multiple local and functional complications may occur. The most frequent include delayed wound healing, nail abnormalities with aesthetic compromise, partial or total nail loss, finger deformities, hypersensitivity, persistent pain, cold intolerance, scar retraction, flexion contractures, chronic ulceration, paresthesias, infection, and necrosis or loss of the reconstructive flap.

Delayed healing is usually related to insufficient debridement of devitalized tissues or, more commonly, excessive tension at closure. This may result in marginal wound necrosis, favoring healing by secondary intention, which occurs progressively through wound contraction and re-epithelialization. (18)

Wound contraction allows the final scar to be considerably smaller than the initial defect; however, poor re-epithelialization may result in suboptimal skin coverage. Retracted scars or atrophic changes in the digital pulp may lead to hypersensitivity of the fingertip. To prevent this complication, reconstruction with sensate flaps that provide

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adequate thickness and restore tactile function is recommended.

Likewise, a shortened nail bed associated with insufficient bony support of the distal phalanx and soft-tissue deficiency may result in nail deformities with unfavorable aesthetic outcomes. Following fingertip amputation, combined loss of bone and soft tissue promotes redundancy of the nail bed, which may fold over the end of the distal phalanx, resulting in the so-called hook nail deformity. This alteration may cause discomfort or pain at the fingertip, interfering with daily activities and representing both a functional and aesthetic problem, particularly in children and young women. (19) Multiple surgical techniques have been described for management of this deformity, including the classic antenna procedure, composite digital pulp graft, homodigital advancement flaps, free tissue transfer, and the triangular oblique neurovascular osteocutaneous flap. (20)

CONCLUSIONS

The fingertip integrates a complex combination of specialized tissues that play a fundamental role in hand function and sensation. Finger injuries most frequently result from the use of hand tools and sharp-edged metal objects and may present as lacerations, partial amputations, or neurovascular compromise. Despite the availability of multiple therapeutic guidelines, management of fingertip injuries remains a topic of debate due to limited evidence conclusively supporting one treatment modality over another.

Inadequate management of fingertip injuries may lead to functional and aesthetic complications, including hook nail deformity, cold intolerance, and cutaneous hypersensitivity. Regardless of the therapeutic strategy employed, early rehabilitation—including early mobilization, splinting, and occupational therapy—is critical for functional recovery and prevention of long-term stiffness.

Clinical outcomes largely depend on the timeliness and adequacy of initial treatment. Available evidence suggests that a multidisciplinary approach involving surgeons, hand therapists, and primary care providers is associated with better functional outcomes. In addition, the psychosocial impact of fingertip injuries, particularly regarding aesthetics and functionality, should be considered as an integral part of patient care.

The incorporation of evidence-based practices, together with a patient-centered approach, allows optimization of clinical decision-making and promotes comprehensive recovery. In this context, care that addresses both physical and psychosocial aspects is essential to improve patients' quality of life. Finally, ongoing research and development of new therapeutic modalities will contribute to refining management strategies, with the goal of achieving better aesthetic, functional, and psychological outcomes in patients with fingertip injuries.

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